

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 1- Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements

D1.1 Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programs

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Abstract :	<p>The task 1.1 has kick-started NEON activities project by conducting deep analysis of considered CECs, with a focus on technical characterization of their energy assets (generation, storage), working profiles, load type (heating/cooling systems, common lightning, etc.), energy requirements and flexibility potential, with a special point of attention for identifying the building efficiency retrofit and cross-service integration opportunities.</p> <p>The report provides an overview of energy efficiency programs and identify suitable mechanisms for cross-service integration</p>
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Executive summary

The Citizen Energy Community (CEC) is a concept introduced with the EU Directive 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity with the goal to define a voluntary legal not-for-profit entity established at a local level for the purpose of energy “generation, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, storage”, etc. In NEON project, four Citizen Energy Communities have been selected (BERCHIDDA in Italy, DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE in France, POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS in Spain and STAINS CITY in France) to represent different techno-economic, societal, and climatic environments and provide suitable testbed for CECs innovative service concepts and business models.

Deliverable 1.1 is the first deliverable of **WP1 Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements** and a result of Task 1.1 **Energy-saving opportunities through cross-service integration**. It aims at systematically analyzing the related case studies and identifying suitable mechanisms for cross-service integration with high energy savings and flexibility potential. Through a series of workshops, the NEON consortium elaborated the context of project CECs and made an audit of CECs and technical characterization of their energy assets (generation, storage), working profiles, load type (heating/cooling systems, common lightning, etc.), energy requirements and flexibility potential, with special care on identifying the building efficiency retrofit and cross-service integration opportunities. The results will be used as input in subsequent WP1 tasks, WP2 tasks and WP3 tasks and will help in focusing the service offer and setting the foundation for business planning.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AEC	Azienda Elettrica Comunale
BIM	Building Information Modeling
BMS	Building Management System
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
DR	Distributed resources
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMD	Electricity Market Directive
ESCo	Energy Services Company
EU	European union
EV	Electric Vehicle
H2	Hydrogen
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
Li-Ion	lithium-ion
P2P	Peer- to-Peer
POD	Point Of Delivery
PV	Photovoltaic
ToU	Time-of-Use
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

NEON project aims at establishment and development of a technical and business ecosystem for integrated energy services for European communities, capable of saving energy, reducing CO₂ emissions, and bringing economic and social benefits, while valorising the energy efficiency and flexibility at demand-side. The project has engaged grid stakeholders, service providers and final consumers to establish, in co-creation, the cross-sectoral arrangements and underlying service concepts.

The NEON objectives are aligned with the directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity. The internal market for electricity has been progressively implemented throughout the Union since 1999 and it aims to deliver real choice for all Union final customers, citizens or businesses, new business opportunities, competitive prices, efficient investment signals and higher standards of service, and to contribute to security of supply and sustainability. The directive (EU) 2019/944 introduced the Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) concept as a category of cooperation of citizens or local actors that should be subject to recognition and protection under Union law with the aim to enable faster market uptake, and facilitate communities, both residential and non-residential, in becoming energy efficient. In NEON, the CECs service concepts and business models will be showcased in 4 CEC setups (BERCHIDDA in Italy, DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE in France, POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS in Spain and STAINS CITY in France) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 7 “follower” communities will be developed during the project.

The NEON work plan is divided into seven Work Packages (WPs)[1], as follows: WP1 on service and business co-creation; WP2 on contracting and financial aspects, WP3 and WP4 on advancing concepts for service operation and verification, WP5 on ethics and impact assessment, WP6 related to dissemination and exploitation and WP7, the project management WP. The interrelation between WPs is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Figure 1: Main interactions of WP1 with other WPs of NEON project

2. NEON's vision and objectives

In today's European civil and industrial society, there is a growing concern about the increasing need for energy consumption, the monopoly in the energy sector and, above all, aspects such as safety, generation, scalability, maintenance, or adaptability of the current electrical grid, within the framework of the needs of modern society.

One of the most relevant aspects is the technological fit of renewable generation systems and their characteristics, such as their dependence on meteorological aspects. This aspect makes the energy flow to be clearly affected by the operation dynamics of renewable generation and establishes the technological bases within the game of electricity supply with the goal of satisfying demand.

These intrinsic aspects of the nature of renewable energies are not modifiable, at least at present, so that the energy balance of society must be established by means of different mechanisms that also explicitly imply the essence of social and technological transformation.

Thus, from a technological innovation point of view, these mechanisms can be focused on the creation of new concepts of efficient energy services. These services should maintain energy efficiency and demand flexibility resources as some of their basic principles.

Based on this approach, it is not technically simple to materialize these premises since, on the one hand, it is based on the commercial and technological concepts already existing in the market but, on the other hand, it is necessary to explore the potential of the flexibility of the services proposed in the project to respond to the demand. The NEON project proposes to combine these concepts through the development of technologically advanced energy control capabilities for the maximum number of buildings and energy assets allowed by current legislation, while maintaining an avant-garde and democratic vision of the European energy sector.

To this end, NEON [1] aims to enable the technical and business ecosystem of integrated energy services for energy communities located in the European territory. Having as a basic principle of integration both energy efficiency and demand, these integrated services aim at better energy management and minimization of energy consumption, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and have a democratic social and economic basis. To this end, the NEON project has the following specific objectives:

- **Objective 1:** Starting from the concepts of holistic optimization, NEON will be able to lay solid technological foundations of energy services based on energy efficiency. Also, starting from the principles of information reusability, NEON will evolve the currently available services and integrate other energy services.
- **Objective 2:** Another important aspect is undoubtedly the interaction and integration of these energy services with existing business models and the adaptation of these models

to new integrated service strategies. Thus, NEON will give rise to innovative business models through integration of EPC (Energy Performance Contracting) and P4P (Pay for Performance) procurement systems in all sectors adapting to different business, regulatory and contractual frameworks.

- **Objective 3:** The aim is to bundle energy benefits with those that are not directly attributable to the energy system. This bundling will be part of integrated services. For this, NEON will use Big Data and ICT tools. Logically, this procedure will respect such vital aspects as the health and privacy of society.
- **Objective 4:** The aim is to enhance the capacity for flexibility by hybridizing a demand and response model. This concept must consider energy demand at the building and community level.
- **Objective 5:** Another technological objective is to optimize the operation and therefore the exploitation of energy efficiency in buildings. NEON aims to realize this objective through the use, development and deployment of advanced control systems and the optimization of building systems.
- **Objective 6:** As the last technical objective of the NEON project, within the compensation and billing system, it will provide novel mechanisms for measuring and verifying performance by applying intelligence principles. This will make use of data-driven analytical services and automated mechanisms for fair distribution of benefits on the DLT platform.

3. Document Objectives and Structure

The task 1.1 kick-starts the NEON project by performing a systematic characterization of the project pilots and providing insight into their energy and flexibility potential. This characterization is carried out from the perspective of existing energy-related infrastructures (e.g., buildings, appliances, networks), while also describing current existing operation scenarios at the pilot sites (e.g., energy services, direct load control, smart home / office services, etc.). This systematic analysis of the related case studies aims to identify the most promising mechanisms for cross-service integration and benefits bundling that will yield significant energy savings and flexibility potential.

This first task has multiple objectives:

- To perform a screening of various flexibility potentials/credits and energy savings by type of usage and technology that will allow the prefeasibility studies for establishing energy communities.
- To consider the integration of energy efficiency and other energy services (such as RES/storage utilization, EV charging scheduling and demand response), and bundling with

non-energy benefits under the user-tailored services (e.g., related to comfort, health and safety aspects).

- To analyse opportunities across different types of consumers, the task will elaborate the context of project CECs in more detail as well.

This deliverable is composed of 10 sections:

- Section 1: An introduction is given to the deliverable giving an overview of the NEON projects aim projects objectives along with the project work plan.
- Section 2: In this section an overview of the documents objectives and structure is given
- Section 3: Gives a detail description of the NEON's vision and objectives.
- Section 4: Describes the NEON's Citizen Energy Communities location.
- Section 5: Provides the assessment of the existing energy efficiency services.
- Section 6: Gives an overview of NEON's CECS existing energy services.
- Section 7: Gives an overview of services cross-integration mechanisms.
- Section 8: Analyses the NEON's CECS cross-services and related business opportunities.
- Section 10: Internal Review.

4. NEON's Citizen Energy Communities

NEON will address the objectives described in section 2 and task 1.1 in section 3 (NEONs objectives), in an integrated manner that will be demonstrated across different demonstration locations. In total, four Citizen Energy Communities activities will be carried out in three different European countries, namely France, Spain, and Italy. Following the beginning of the NEON project, to develop a homogeneous description of each pilot, the following categories for pilot technical characterization have been proposed:

- Location
- Pilot stakeholders and roles
- Building type
- Energy sources and infrastructure
- Current operations
- Energy demand characteristics
- Flexibility potential

The "Location" category describes the location as well as important geographical and meteorological characteristics of the pilot. Meteorological conditions are important variables that impact energy demand and local production forecasts. "Pilot stakeholders and roles" are used to describe the actors of the pilots and their relationships with the NEON project. Building type describes the technical assets that are known to be existing and available at the pilot sites. These are three general characteristics of the pilot sites, which will be refined when specific households are recruited, as some individual building types or appliances may vary between households. The

“Energy sources and infrastructure” category includes the external energy infrastructures, such as shared local renewable generation plants, heating networks, electric distribution networks, IT networks and their characteristics. The “Current operation scenarios at pilot sites” category details user stories, control strategies, communities, or involvement of inhabitants at the pilot sites, in case such initiatives have already been implemented. The “Energy demand characteristics” category describes the current understanding of the local energy demand characteristics, based on the available data for each pilot site. The “Flexibility potential” category outlines the first assessment of the flexibility potential of the pilot site according to the “pre-recruitment” knowledge. It outlines the types of energy uses that could be candidates for demand response/load shifting, communication devices that are in place or could be installed in the near future, or existing interfaces for flexibility incentives or interaction with the end users.

CEC 01: BERCHIDDA, Berchidda Municipality, Italy

Location

Located on the southern slopes of Mount Limbara, in the north of Sardinia Island, Berchidda is a village with 3,000 inhabitants, with Neoclassical and Art Nouveau houses positioned in a “crescent” shape town. The land covers approx. 201km² and it is located at an average altitude of 300 m. The anthropic structures, vegetation and climatic conditions are typical for the inland areas of Sardinia, with average temperatures of 15°C.

Figure 2 Aerial view of the city of Berchidda

Pilot stakeholders and roles

The Berchidda pilot can in turn provide valuable insights on how to implement, communicate and incentivize participatory CEC in small/medium towns, which represent the most common settlement configuration not only in Italy but also in Europe.

Berchidda Municipality is already engaged in the Covenant of Mayors, with the aim of achieving energy independence and reduce energy dissipation, regain, and strengthen the local economy, increase the resident population, home renovation. Berchidda is one of the few municipalities in Italy which owns the electricity grid. The Municipality owns the last mile, and together with Azienda Elettrica Comunale (AEC) operates of a DSO. Recently, the Administration acquired the electricity network of the rural area from Enel Distribution with the plan to upgrade its facilities to an urban microgrid. They aim at merging the rural and the urban grids. More specifically:

- Berchidda has carried out a major renovation of the agricultural grid with the construction of the new electrical cabins.
- It has planned to extend the use of smart meters to the historic centre as well.
- It is building a free communication network that interconnects all users.
- It will be possible to integrate the energy production that takes place in the municipal area, photovoltaic and wind power. There’s also a plan for extension with offshore wind power.

In Berchidda there is a smart grid – Berchidda Energy 4.0 – for remote management and control, smart billing, balancing. Berchidda Municipality operates a platform for energy management, grid balancing and reporting of network faults. Specifically:

- There are 25 MV/LV power substations, equipped with transformers of 100 kVA-500 kVA, for a total power installed of about 5000 kVA.
- There will be 400 buildings equipped with smart power meters for total consumption that will be installed by GridAbility.
- There is the possibility of registering hourly to 15 minutes granularity data for all these buildings, both for production and consumption.

Type of demand	Electricity [MWh/yr]
Residential buildings	2,762.22
Tertiary buildings	414.59
Public buildings	369.12
Industry	2,216.16
TOTAL	5,762.09

Table 1 BERCHIDDA energy consumption

There's an extensive PV production already in place: 67 active PV plants with a total capacity of 608 kW and energy production about 820 MWh/yr.

- 62 private PV plants (800 kWp)
- 3 municipal plants (220 kW)
- 2 industrial plants (130 kW)
- Planned for decentralized PV system (aprox 1,100 MWh production)
- 12% is local production, while 88% is energy purchase from the grid.

Most of the PV installations existing in Berchidda belong to private homes, which utilise them for instantaneous self-consumption; the surplus of electricity produced is sold back to the grid. The first installation of PV for self-consumption dates to 2011, followed by other installations until today. The development of local PV production has been prompted by individual emulation rather than a collective, coordinated move.

In Berchidda, the electricity distribution system operator is a public body that operates beyond commercial logic. It is in the public interest to:

- Develop the use of renewable energy
- Federate cabinets (thus going beyond 120 households) under the same REC
- Maximise the reliance on local production
- Sell to the network only extra production

Since the Municipality owns the electricity distribution network, it is not bound by the current regulatory limits of the Renewable Energy Communities but allows the use of all the technologies and services of the smart grids. The goal of the Italian legislation is to gradually allow the transition from a "virtual" management of energy grids and balances to a more "physical" management where space is given to "prosumer aggregators". Having the Municipality as DSO allows implementing a physical configuration of CER and enact RED II fully:

- The PV is connected to individual households and there is a shared POD (Point Of Delivery)
- It is possible to match physical configuration with the virtual one
- It is possible to propose economic incentives to align consumption with PV production
- Last-mile data are accessible

Figure 3 Physical configuration for the “energy community” foreseen in Berchidda

The Italian pilot involves the following main stakeholders (individual and collective ones):

- **GridAbility** - Pilot coordinator: citizen engagement; interface with the municipality; blockchain-based platform and automated smart DR settlement; installation of smart meters.
- **AEC, the Berchidda Municipality electricity company**, simplifies the constellation of stakeholders typically involved in the energy market. Indeed, the Municipality has a double role of the grid operator and DSO and public administration representing the citizens. AEC is not a separate legal entity: it is a department of the Municipality. The engagement of the Municipality’s technical office is crucial for the technical installations; the engagement of the mayor and his staff is essential in motivating the citizens to participate in the EU projects (like HESTIA, LocalRES, NEON), to disseminate basic information about energy and demand response, and to ensure a long-term engagement of the citizens.
- **AXPO** - Local energy provider and ESCo, serving the Berchidda Municipality: support in deployment activities; validation analysis.

- **MIDAC** - high-capacity lithium-ion (Li-Ion) batteries provider: installation; provision of relevant know-how on battery integration and optimal management
- **Energy4com** (<https://energy4com.eu/>) is an Italian cooperative startup that will support the Municipality in creating a local energy community. It partners already with GridAbility
- **Citizens, SMEs and Industries** are the primary beneficiary of the Berchidda Smart Grid 4.0 and the key actor in enhancing demand response and adjusting their energy behaviours and consumption to reach the communities' objectives. Berchidda inhabitants will be addressed with general communications to improve the adoption of the innovative solutions and increase the number of members of the energy community in the long run.

Figure 4 BERCHIDDA power system architecture

Building type

Berchidda counts 1792 buildings, made of single houses and blocks of flats: over 88% of residential buildings have 1 to 2 floors above ground; buildings with 3 or more floors represent only 12% of the total residential building stock. 50% of the buildings have been built before 1961. Over 98% of the buildings are built with load-bearing masonry, mostly made of “cantonetti” (granite portative elements).

In Berchidda homes, typical common household energy systems include:

- **Heating:** fireplaces.
- **Cooling:** possibility of individual air-conditioning on a case-by-case. The control of these appliances will be performed by their users based on behavioral demand response.
- **Domestic hot water:** electric boilers controllable with an on/off systems.
- **Appliances:** standard such as lighting, fridges, washing machines, dishwashers. Cooking stoves and ovens are powered by gas. The characteristics of these specific appliances will be obtained for each pilot participant after the recruitment phase.
- **Fiscal meters:** the installation of 30 smart meters is foreseen at first in households participating to the HESTIA project, to additional 20 households participating to the LocalRES project, and will be extended over time to reach 100 users by the end of 2030. Smart meters will be owned by the Municipality and provided by Landys and NesosNet (the second is part of the GridAbility joint venture).

Energy sources and infrastructure

Berchidda counts 68 PV plants (800 kWp total), of which 62 are owned by individual citizens, while the others belong to local companies and the Municipality. The PV installations provide 12% of

energy on an annual basis (comparison between annual energy needs of Berchidda and annual PV generation). The rest of the energy is purchased from the grid. The access to PV load curve data will be made possible within LocalRES with the installation of the previously described smart meters and the associated local radio transmitter and gateway. The precise technical characteristics of the installed PV plants for each recruited household will be obtained from the pilot participants after the recruitment phase. The installation of additional 20 heat pumps, storage capacity and public EV charging stations is envisioned as part of the LocalRES project.

Current Operations

Four hundred buildings are monitored with smart power meters for total consumption (15 min/hourly data). Additional smart metering is envisioned under EPC models to disaggregate the energy loads, with deployment of home automation devices to enable demand adjustments. There are different tariffs for electricity depending on the time of use and wholesale market indexes.

Energy demand characteristics

The current aggregated electricity demand for the city of Berchidda is 6500 MWh, which also includes the energy consumption of around 200 SMEs. The largest part of households' energy demand comes from DHW, lighting, and the other specific electric appliances. The average household consumption amounts to 2,436 kWh/year. Following figure illustrates the typical daily net and gross load for the city of Berchidda.

Flexibility potential

Flexibility in Berchidda will be driven by two main forces: load-shifting and digitalization. For what concerns load shifting, the goal is to stimulate more efficient use of energy by shifting part of the evening consumption to the production times of the photovoltaic plants. This provides a load-shifting of 20% of the load in terms of power included in the time range 18:30-23:00 to transfer it to the 11:30-16:00 time slot, which corresponds to about 5% of daily energy, or about 800 kWh/day (292 MWh/year). The estimate is based on the whole population of Berchidda and existing literature.

Possible estimated load after load shifting and digitalization

With the introduction of intelligent measuring devices and an improved awareness on their energy consumption, domestic users are more inclined to act with energy saving in mind, which translates into a reduction of the consumed energy estimated to 8%. Based on this hypothesis and bearing in mind that the domestic users of the municipality of Berchidda accounts for 44% of the total energy consumed in the municipality, figure 3 displays the possible decrease of the global load curve on a typical day.

Figure 5 Estimated load after load shifting and digitalization

CEC 02 : DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE, Villard de Lans, France

Location

“Domaine de la source” CEC is located in a town Villard de Lans, a ski resort of the massif “Vercors” in the French Alps. It represents the town with the largest available lodging in the Vercors Regional Natural Park.

Pilot stakeholders and roles

The service provider is ALB (CTX as LTP).

Building type

The buildings of the CEC have been erected in 2016, and occupied from early 2017, for both lodging and permanent residence. They are made in accordance with the French Thermal Regulation, out of a poured concrete with exterior insulation. Currently this community consists of 25 dwellings in 3 buildings with a potential outreach of 500 dwellings in town under service.

Energy sources and infrastructure

Currently, 3 air-source heat pumps (HP) of 9 kW are in place for hot water production. For heating, the HPs are coupled over the 500L hot water tank and pipelines to the radiant floor. The DHW is produced by two electric boilers of 28.8kW each. DHW is also preheated by the HPs, coupled with the electric boilers over 1000 l water tank. PV panels with 45kWp are installed in 2019 on the south oriented rooftops (15% RES share).

Current Operations

The electricity produced is used for self-consumption, the remaining being sold to the grid. Electricity consumption of individual apartments is monitored, as well as the HPs used for hot water production. Diehl Sharky meters are used for thermal energy and DHW metering. Through “Linky” meters, production, self-consumption, and energy export are monitored. Currently, electricity is provided to the final customers only with Time-of-Use (ToU) tariffing.

Energy demand characteristics

Electricity consumption breakdown: boiler room 140 MWh/y (approx. half for HPs and half for electrical boilers); common areas 65 MWh/y (ventilation, elevators, electric snow melting, common lightning; 1750 kWh/y per apartment.

Flexibility potential

Considering that demo buildings are in fact individual prosumers, NEON will aim to enable an optimized interaction between the consumers and grid. Storing the thermal energy and HP operation will be considered for optimization to provide optimal building operation, improved indoor environment and flexibility services. This will be enabled by remote integration with the central control unit which manages HP operation. It is expected that NEON enables higher RES exploitation, while unlocking the demand flexibility (both electrical and thermal). Currently, electricity is provided to the final customers only with Time-of-Use (ToU) tariffing, which is expected to evolve to variable pricing scheme during the NEON project. Joint EPC and P4P

contracting will be considered to enable further building improvements and flexibility sharing. Services will be delivered by ALB, while providing aggregation of community-level demand.

Figure 6 DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE

CEC 03 : POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS, Villacañas (Toledo), Spain

Location

CEC is in a town Villacañas (Toledo) about 100km from Madrid. Traditionally it has maintained an important industrial development linked to the agro-food industry and the construction of wooden doors, with exports all over the world.

Pilot stakeholders and roles

The service provider is APPA (GFM as LTP). GFM will assume the role of an energy provider and ESCO, engaged in service delivery. The business models will include dynamic pricing schemes (only a ToU tariffing now), designed on top of the distributed energy resource management programs (e.g., integrating EV charging).

Building type

The CEC is composed of 5 industrial facilities/buildings of the industrial park Las Cabezas (three wooden doors manufacturing companies , a cheese company, and a catering company) and 10 preselected residential houses, while 10 more will be engaged during the project. GFM is a company based in the industrial area, specialized in the installation and maintenance of RES, mainly PVs. This community has a potential outreach of 100 companies and 25 houses under service.

Energy sources and infrastructure

GFM has PV installations on its building's rooftops with a power of 64 kW for self-consumption and 400 kW for integration into the network. GFM obtained financing for a Phase 2 SME Instrument project called SunninBox, which realized a decentralized portable PV energy network capable of providing 10 kW in each installation point. In addition, the demo site has a wind turbine, 3 EV chargers and a lead-acid battery.

Current Operations

Generated electricity will be used for self-consumption, while selling the excess energy to grid. Monitoring infrastructure for electricity consumption and PV production is already in place.

Energy demand characteristics

In total, 560 kW of electricity production is available. In addition, the demo site has 30kWp wind turbine, 3 EV chargers (90kW fast, 2x7.4kW allowing V2G/V2B) and 40kWh lead-acid battery (OPzV).

Flexibility potential

Leveraging the optimal energy asset scheduling, NEON will set up a Virtual Power Plant (VPP) by uniting all the existing renewable plants at a single point, so the demo site behaves as a single network. This way, NEON will form a portfolio of ‘dispatchable’ and ‘non-dispatchable’ energy sources, capable of performing the optimal energy dispatching and building control while respecting the needs of the end consumers (both industrial and residential), to provide sufficient flexibility, reliable energy supply and network services. As a result, NEON will enable cheaper energy for local community, improve the impact on the environment, reduce interruptions due to peak demand in the network and offer greater flexibility to the grid. Optimal operation of buildings (electrical loads, heating/cooling) will be provided, while ensuring higher exploitation of locally produced energy, and unlocking the demand flexibility. Upgrading the storage capacities or building improvements (e.g., wall insulation) will be considered as part of the underlying business models and operational strategies. Peer- to-Peer (P2P) trading will be considered for transactions and energy exchange between producers.

Figure 7 POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL CEC

CEC 04: STAIN City, Stains, FRANCE

Location

Under “**Inventons la Metropole du Grand Paris**” competition, the consortium managed by ENGIE was chosen as the winner to develop a real estate complex for office, business, parking use and services (catering, retail, hotel). The complex is located on two sites, with an area of 29,185m² for business establishments, and 5,330m² for services and parking areas, respectively. ENGIE lab

CRIGEN building located on the primary site, consists of 8,773m² accommodating offices, industrial premises, and laboratories.

Pilot stakeholders and roles

The service provider for this energy community is ENGIE.

Building type

This energy community currently consists of 2 buildings/sites, area of approximately 34,500m² with a potential outreach of 4 similar office buildings under service. Thanks to the concept of digital BIM, the building meets the requirements of E+C- French label. The main framework of the building is based on metal posts, beams, and purlins, while the facade walls are made of cross-laminated solid wood panels.

Energy sources and infrastructure

Gas absorption HPs and reversible chillers ensure the low heating and air conditioning. Heat recovery is provided on AHUs using a plate exchanger. The heating room is transformed into a living lab thanks to the bypass installation on the primary network of innovative technologies for performance tests, e.g., fuel cells (natural gas and hydrogen). Fan coils and radiant panels are used to achieve uniform temperature across building area, and to provide flexibility from the grid point of view. Innovative technologies on the roof: last generation PV (minimum 30m²), H₂ panel thanks for solar electrolysis (15m²), and solar thermal panel (10m²). The neighbours with PV potential are already made part of the energy community after the first design phase.

Current Operations

The control functions are enabled by a BMS with 4000 data points, allowing remote access and supervision. The ventilation flow is controlled based on occupancy.

Energy demand characteristics

Flexibility potential

Electricity and thermal consumption of the demo site will be compensated by the local production. The H₂ production from the H₂ panels will be stored and used thanks to the fuel cells. Installation of batteries and additional PVs will be considered for provision of electricity for recharging 2 EV stations. The office building of the ENGIE lab CRIGEN will be a part of the wider CEC. Activity for expanding the local energy community, considering the business model as well, will be partially done in NEON. The excess electricity from PVs will be distributed to the neighbourhood or exchanged with the grid. Innovative business models based on investment cost in energy assets will be explored as part of the EPC contractual arrangements. The hybrid heat pumps installed for heating and cooling of the offices, which run on electricity and/or gas will be exploited to provide the flexibility for improved grid operation, while coupling energy and non-energy benefits. The objectives of demo activities are to identify the viability of relevant business models owing to preliminary energy performance assessment, and to implement cost-effective use cases while enhancing the sector coupling at building and district level. Local authorities such as the city major will be involved in the valorization and scale up of the results.

Figure 8 Stain City Office complex

5. Existing energy efficiency services assessment methodology

The assessment of the existing energy efficiency services offered by NEON CEC's stakeholders is the first action to consider in the CECs services creation process. Therefore, it is pivotal to understand and describe the existing energy services offered by NEON's emerging CECs, and to identify the different actors and their links with the services within each CEC environment. Being able to describe and compare these services, will allow us to identify the potential future interactions between this existing energy, and to determine the future opportunities to be created within each CEC environment as a whole.

This section provides a description of a common methodology based on the Service Blueprint technique. This methodology has been implemented by T1.1 participants to identify, describe in detail and to analyse the existing services offered by NEON CEC's.

5.1. Definitions

Four Key concepts have been addressed within T1.1 activities, namely Citizen Communities, Citizen Energy Communities, Energy Service, Cross-services Integration. At the outset, these key concepts have been based on WP1 participants' understanding and then according to EU directives.

- **Citizen communities:** Local initiatives or cooperatives based on active participation and collective decisions, that work towards a shared goal of generating common benefits.

- **Citizen energy communities:** Legal entities made of citizen-led and local initiatives that self-produce and consume renewable energies, and are paving the path towards decentralization, decarbonization and democratization of our energy system.
This concept has been defined by the **Article 2(11)** of the Electricity Market Directive (**EMDI**) as a legal entity that:
 - (a) is based on voluntary and open participation and is effectively controlled by members or shareholders that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises.
 - (b) has for its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic, or social community benefits to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits; and
 - (c) may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders.
- **Service:** solutions to customers and/or citizen-related problems, to increase welfare and generate local value.
- **Cross service integration:** Orchestration of interoperable services to provide value, based on cross-fertilization & synergies, to answer with dedicated solutions to expectation/needs from heterogeneous environment.

5.2. Existing energy services assessment process

The objective of NEON's Task 1.1: Energy-saving opportunities through cross-service integration reported in this document is to perform analysis of NEON's emerging or existing Citizen Energy Communities and the associated existing energy services related to potential energy flexibility and to energy saving according to type of usage and technology with a special emphasis on the building energy efficiency. Additionally, this task aims to identify suitable mechanisms for cross-integration of existing services, as well as mechanisms that allow developing new services within the community thus offering new business opportunities.

Having the objectives of the pilots being identified, the activities (assessment of existing energy services and potential cross-integration) have been conducted in two main steps:

- **Preparation and concepts definition**

This first step was undertaken by organizing a workshop with all WP1 partners and elaborating the key elements in a collaborative manner, as follows

1. T1.1 key concepts definition, namely: Energy communities, citizen energy communities, service, cross service –integration, as described in the previous section.
2. The service criteria list to be used for the energy services selection within the analysis process.

The criteria list defined by WP1 partners to help the selection and the prioritization of the existing services as presented in the Annex I of this document.

- The definition of model to be used for the service’s description in a multidimensional way, as a tool to be used in the design of the service’s cross integration.

The adapted blueprint canvas, with localization, environmental and economic dimension, has been shared with T1.1 participants and used for the services description in a multidimensional way.

Figure 9 NEON'S T1.1 Step 01 workshop collaborative board

- Services selection and description**

This phase focused on the identification of the services that exist within each NEON’s CECs perimeter i.e., those that meet the selection criteria identified by T1.1 participants in the first workshop. Furthermore, pilot partners described the selected service (one by one within each CEC) in a complete, step by step and multidimensional manner. This description was carried out on in two stages:

1. **Service identity card:** using the value statement template presented below.

Service Value Statement	
OUR Name of the service	<input type="text"/>
IS Category of the service	<input type="text"/>
THAT Benefit of the service	<input type="text"/>
FOR Customer description	<input type="text"/>
WHO Need or opportunity	<input type="text"/>
UNLIKE Market leader / reference competitor	<input type="text"/>

Figure 10 Value Statement Template

This template is a descriptive tool that expresses the service value proposition in one clear and concise sentence.

It answers the "what is your service"- and the "why someone should buy and use it" questions.

2. **Service Blueprint:** using the Blueprint template presented below.

Figure 11 Service Multi-dimensional Blueprint template

This model corresponds to a modified multidimensional Blueprint and aims at describing a given service. It visualizes the components of a service in enough detail to analyze, implement, and improve it. The template also shows the orchestration of people, touchpoints, processes, and technology both frontstage (what customers see) and backstage (what is behind the scenes).

The model was used in an autonomous way by the pilots to describe the services identified (the activities, actors involved, in what form, etc.).

The Blueprint template is filled up: **first horizontally** by describing the actors' journeys step by step, **then vertically** – column by column to match the interactions between them.

For each of the selected services from the "Existing Services Selection Grid», the pilots' leaders had to define:

A/ The customer journey by:

- Indicating the name and the location of the customer.
- Describing the customer journey step by step.

B/ The front-stage actors and actions by:

- Indicating the name and the location of the front-stage actors.
- Specifying whether it is an internal resource or an external partner.
- Describing each front-stage actor activities / actions in interaction with the customer (under the actions of the customer therefore, in column).
- Adding as many actions per actor as needed.
- Adding as many front-stage actors as needed.

C/ The touch points by:

- Indicating the touchpoints (at each step of the customer journey) that are used by the customer during his interaction with the service and the front-stage actors.
- Describing the customer journey step by step.
- Adding as many as touchpoints as needed along the customer journey.

D/ The back-stage actors and actions by:

- Indicating the name and the location of the back-stage actors.
- Specifying whether it is an internal resource or an external partner.
- Describing each back-stage actor activities / actions (before, during and after the actions of the customer and the front-stage actors, in column).
- Adding as many actions per actor as needed.

- Adding as many back-stage actors as needed.

E/ The internal process/Technologies/Tools

- Indicate the internal processes / technologies / tools (before, during and after the customer journey and front-stage actions, in column) that are used by the front stage and the back-stage actors to deliver the service.
- Add as many internal processes/technologies/tools as needed.
- Add as many internal processes / technologies / tools as needed.

F/ The environmental impact

Indicate the possible environmental impact of each step by adding: (- -) no impact, (-) low impact, (+) strong impact, (++) very strong impact.

G/The Business impact

Indicate the business impact of each step by adding a qualitative information: costs (-), costs (+), revenue (-), revenue (+).

H/Steps and temporality

Finally add temporal elements at key moments of the service.

The work performed within this second phase allows us to (1) have a clear understanding on what already exists, and which services could be provided by NEON's CECs, and (2) to describe in a step-by-step manner the services actors' journey and to match the interactions between them. This will also enable us to compare these services based on the service backstage activities, services frontstage activities, their business and environmental impact, and to identify synergies, interdependencies and consider their cross-integration.

6. NEON's CECs Existing energy services Overview

6.1. CEC 01 - BERCHIDDA services

Here follows a list of the existing CEC services in the Berchidda Municipality.

Local Energy Community

The Local Energy Community is a **non-technical service that aims to set up the social engagement and energy awareness among all the Berchidda electricity residential customers that want to**

engage into behavioral change and citizen community engagement, differing from **other** community practices with no explicit collective energy saving goals.

Involved partners in this service provision are GridAbility and Energy4com, working in tandem with the Berchidda Municipality.

Several activities are put in place to deliver the service to the target users, including social engagement and animation community meetings, awareness-raising events, social media, and editorial activities. Ethnographic research methodologies have been deployed to deliver the service, including survey questionnaire, interviews and focus groups organized involving main stakeholders (citizens, SMEs, industries, local municipality representatives, etc).

In building the Local Energy Community that the Municipality is working to establish, the next new following energy services will be deployed: highly efficient electrical heat pump systems and EV recharging stations with the LocalRES EU Project, battery energy storage systems with the HESTIA EU Project and new PV plants on residential houses of the members of the community via private investments. These services will be connected by means of specific smart meters deployed by Gridability and an energy community platform developed by Prosume that will enable collection of data and shaping of business logics as established by the Berchidda Community.

Thus, this service will join social benefits through engagement and disseminating events, comfort benefits offering additional services to the community (improved and energy saving heating and cooling system delivering at the same time higher quality of comfort at all times, and EV recharging stations), and metering and monitoring services for a better and optimized management of the energy system and to increase the members awareness, coupled with dynamic energy audits offered by R2M Energy to the members of the community.

Collective self-consumption of PV production

The collective self-consumption of PV production is an energy-sharing service tailoring to the **electricity residential customers of the Berchidda CEC that already have PV panel installed (prosumer) , and aims to exploit the national incentives for RES self-consumption**, unlike other residents with PV panel installed not belonging to the CEC.

Involved partners in this service provision are GridAbility (via Nesosnet and PROSUME), together with AXPO, in tandem with the Berchidda Municipality (via AEC).

Several activities are put in place to deliver the service to the target users, including several community meetings, as well as technical meetings with the partners involved in the service provision. Moreover, the Nesosnet Community Platform and the Prosumer App are in the development phase and target to be delivered to the end users (first beta version) in April 2022. The service is, furthermore, leveraging on available means including active control of storage capacity (connected to 30 MIDAC storage batteries), demand response (connected to DEVELCO smart monitoring system in 30 homes), the Nesosnet fiscally certified smart meters (IoT Energy

Hub) and community platform, as well as the municipality distribution grid and baseline electric consumption data.

While Service 1 and Service 2 are, at the very moment of production of this deliverable, the only 2 existing services we can highlight at the Berchidda Pilot site, it is worth being mentioned a wide array of energy-flexibility and energy-efficiency services are planned to be delivered within the soon-to-be established Energy Community. These include, but not limit to 15 **RES energy services** have been identified as follows:

1. P2H (and H2P)
2. Building heating optimization (systems and electricity consumption optimization)
3. Collective Peak shaving
4. REC/Collective self-consumption
5. Optimisation of energy flows within the REC
6. Demand response (Implicit and explicit)
7. V2G services
8. P2P energy trading
9. Aggregated (REC-level) energy trading
10. Public EV (Electric Vehicles) charging stations
11. Smart Storage Management System
12. Capitalisation of monitored data
13. Legal advice
14. Preliminary feasibility assessment
15. End-user engagement

Figure 12 Berchidda Future Energy Service Development Plan 0 reference LocalRES project

6.2. CEC02 - DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE services

During the interview phase, three main energy efficiency services have been identified for Domaine de la Source CEC:

- Power to Grid: Extended community to maximize self-consumption.
- Energy efficiency: reduction of energy production losses.
- Sobriety: engaging occupants in energy sobriety.

Power to grid

The objective of this service is to achieve 100% self-consumption in order to maximize the profits related to the local production of electricity from the solar power plant. The diagram below details the current business model.

Thus far, 40% of production is sold to EDF at a price of €60/MWh; 60% is self-consumed by the DDLS site with significant losses in the production of heat and domestic hot water (DHW). This service should lead to the reduction of resale to EDF as much as possible by maximizing self-consumption with the sale of energy at a price negotiated in the energy community higher than the EDF tariff. This will only be possible by extending the community to the district or town of Villard de Lans. A meeting with the mayor of Villard de Lans is scheduled for January 2023 in order to align on the support to be provided by the municipality. The key data of this service are:

- Accurate updated state of energy flows.
- Economic model with the extended community.

Energy efficiency

The design of the heating and domestic hot water production installations did not incorporate flexibility in the occupation of the dwellings. As a result, production is centralized and distributed by two hot water loops, one for heating and another one for domestic hot water (DHW), whether the building is occupied by 1 dwelling or 25 dwellings.

Energy losses are therefore significant but partly absorbed (financially) by solar self-consumption. It is therefore essential to optimize heat production to maximize the value of photovoltaic solar production.

The key data of this service is the energy audit outputs.

Sobriety

The 15-unit building is largely used as a secondary residence, only 7 units are continuously occupied. The inhabitants are not very aware of the need to save energy, moreover this energy seems free because it is produced by solar panels. Some dwellings remain heated at 22°C all year round. It is therefore important to take advantage of the creation of the energy community to engage the inhabitants in a more economical approach. This service will be provided through the use of an appropriate software to raise awareness among occupants, and to support them in a behaviour change process. Indeed, the economic interest takes precedence in the result of this operation.

The key data of this service are:

- Accurate economic model of the impact of energy waste.
- Consumption data.

6.3. CEC 03 - POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS services

This pilot is in Villacañas (Spain). Existing services are installed on headquarters of GFM (Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas) and they are working on their own, according to the Spanish regulations. Each energy service has its own regulatory aspects. The aim of this CEC is to take advantage of existing services in order to be able to make use of both surplus production and the availability of a storage system. The shared use of energy, seeking its direct use, can help to promote a more efficient use of energy from renewable sources.

PV Self consumption system

The owner (GFM) of this existing energy service uses the energy generated by its PV self-consumption system for own uses and reducing the dependence of grid company. GFM needs electricity for its activities and its prices are increasing considerably. That is the reason one of these kinds of solutions is installed. All electricity which is produced is directly consumed, in this way, the installation aims to be as efficient as possible, consuming energy as it is generated.

The surplus generation is stored in batteries (third energy existing service) and if batteries are full is fed into the grid (a special discount in electricity bills is done thanks to this energy).

In this process of energy treatment, two figures are involved which, although they are not part of the project, are necessary to consider as they will determine the economic performance of the installation as well as its availability to be connected to the distribution network.

On the one hand we have Unión Fenosa which is the electricity distribution company. It oversees carrying electricity to GFM headquarters (voltage and frequency). It is also needing for an appropriate PV self-consumption behaviour. If there is not voltage and frequency, PV inverters will not work due to an anti-islanding protection.

On the other hand, we find Gesternova (market agent). It is the responsible for billing for electricity.

For making possible these services some activities are required: engineering project, legalization (administration and grid company), equipment installation (PV modules and PV inverters), device programming and maintenance tasks (O&M).

The available means are:

- 104 PV modules.
- 6 PV inverters.
- PV structure.
- Monitoring system.
- Meter.

EV Recharging station

The recharging point that will be part of the community is owned by GFMCA, so it will be this company that will be directly involved with the CEC.

In order to establish a charging point, as with any installation, it will be necessary to obtain the necessary permits from the energy distribution company. Once access has been granted, it will be necessary to have a specific regulated electricity tariff for electric vehicles and, finally, a platform where users can connect and recharge and make the corresponding payments.

In the case of the electric vehicle recharging point installed at CEC03, the energy supply has been contracted with the electricity supplier called "Gesternova" and "Electromaps" is currently used as the platform on which to carry out the transactions for recharging at the point. The electricity distribution company, as in the case of generation, is "Unión Fenosa", which is responsible for guaranteeing the quality of the electricity supply within the current regulations, ensuring that the network has appropriate frequency and voltage values for use by any end user connected to its network.

GFMCA, for its part, will be responsible for carrying out the engineering work on the charger such as technical drawings, legalisation, obtaining permits, installation of any equipment or protections necessary for the start-up of the charger, as well as contracting the manager of the recharging point and, lastly, carrying out preventive and corrective maintenance of the charger.

The charger has different possibilities for charging an electric vehicle, having available a maximum power of 50kW distributed in 40kW in AC and 50kW in DC. So, if only one socket is used, it will charge at maximum power and if two are used at the same time, the power will be distributed between the two sockets.

The inclusion of a charging point in the community will have positive connotations when considering electric vehicles as zero emission vehicles, especially if we can take advantage of the

solar potential available for charging at the time of solar energy production. Consumers will then be able to charge their vehicles directly with the energy obtained from the sun.

Energy storage

The owner (GFM) of this existing energy service uses the surplus energy generated by its PV self-consumption system for storage using lead acid batteries. It is a way for reducing the dependence of energy from the electricity company.

There are two others involved collaborators. These ones will not participate in our future energy community, but they are mandatory for electrical supply to GFM according to Spanish regulation.

On the one hand we have Unión Fenosa which is the electricity distributor. It oversees carrying electricity to GFM headquarters (voltage and frequency). It is also needing for an appropriate storage system behaviour. If there is not voltage and frequency, battery will not work due to an anti-islanding protection. Despite this, there would be a circuit for critical loads always available. On the other hand, we find Gesternova (market agent). It is the responsible for billing for electricity.

For making possible these services some activities are required: engineering project, legalization (administration and grid company), equipment installation (lead acid batteries and batteries inverters), device programming activities and operation and maintenance tasks (O&M).

The available means are:

- 48 batteries (2V, 1000Ah, 48V).
- 3 inverters/chargers' batteries.
- Monitoring system.
- Meter.
- Anti-islanding device.

6.4. CEC 04 -STAINS CITY services

Listed below, a short description of the energy services that already exists among CEC STAIN CITY Stakeholders, the detailed description is provided on the services blueprint on **Annex II**.

Facility management

This service concerns all the office complex, it is provided at both ENGIE building and Industreet building. This service is mainly used by the complex office's occupants, but also by the property manager who guarantees an efficient exploitation and technical maintenance of the building's equipment.

The facility management is an operation service that aims to reduce the global energy consumption of the building, secure an efficient operation by optimally control the different assets, create flexibility using optimal scheduling, define the building load shifting mechanisms, and improve the environmental impact of the building while guaranteeing the comfort and security of the office occupants.

This facility manager is hired in general by the property manager, to supervise and maintain the building operation. However, the facility management operation and service could be strongly impacted and conditioned by: 1)- the energy providers (that sells the energy to the building occupants), 2)- the Building Management System (BMS) integrator , which is responsible for setting up the control system of the building and managing the HVAC consumption profiles.

PV production and self-consumption

The PV production self-consumption in an energy supply service, provided by the INDUSTREET that owns a 180 KWp rooftop PV installation. This installation produces local renewable energy for individual self-consumption.

This service is currently and exclusively used by Industreet, that produces its own solar energy and uses it locally used to satisfy partially the building occupants energy demand.

The PV self-consumption service allows, through a green and local energy production, to reduce the energy supply cost for the office building, limit the dependency on the grid, and control the energy bill by consuming free energy at the peak periods. This service also generates extra incomes for INDUSTREET by selling the surplus of their daily production.

Today, Industreet targets to maximize as much as possible their self-consumption capabilities, to avoid cutting off a part of the surplus when the energy produced is not in totality required by the building occupants, but also to avoid any injection to the grid and avoid the constraints pushed by the DSO.

Green H2 production

The H2 production services an energy supply service owned by ENGIE, today used for research purposes to learn from real-scale demonstrations.

This service is used by ENGIE collaborators and the Hydrogen research lab -ENGIE for: 1)- hydrogen provisioning technologies testing and validation, 2) exploring new areas of expertise and to develop green and carbon-free energy sources.

ENGIE through this power-to-gas technology targets to produce hydrogen and power from exclusively green and renewable sources to be used afterward for: 1)- green mobility for both EV and FCEV, 2) for power-to-power systems to inject electric power to the grid via the fuel cells .

This service could generate incomes if the H2 produced is sold or in exchange for other services (example: agreements with the municipality).

7. Services Cross-integration

By cross-integrating existing services, we seek to create opportunities for shared and local services within NEON's Citizen Energy Communities.

We therefore seek to condense the value chain, decompartmentalize the jobs/professions, better connect with the ecosystem, share resources, means or technologies to create new opportunities and to boost growth.

In the section we propose an overview of cross-integration mechanisms to identify within this task, followed by the process proposed to T1.1 participants to help them to cross-integrate the existing services among the stakeholders and to create new opportunities within their CECs.

7.1. Cross-integration mechanisms overview

- **Union:** [4]close relationship / reunion between two or more "things" to form a homogeneous whole / become one.

This mechanism provides simplicity, the services united will not necessarily become one and unique service. It could be interrelation and liaison of the services without fusion.

In the case of a CEC stakeholders should first identify the requirements of the union, determine rules for the deployment of the energy services and agree on them.

- **Combination:** [3][4] joining or merging of different "things" in which the component elements are individually distinct.

Unlike the union, the combination consists of merging the services to allow them to work in collaborative way. This mechanism requires less alignment between the services to cross-integrate, however, the added value may be less important than when using more complex mechanisms.

- **Symbiotic:** [5] association of two or more dissimilar organisms, mutual advantages and disadvantages, overall benefits for the whole.

The benefits of the symbiotic mechanism are often very interesting. This mechanism consists of addition the capacities of all the partners and modify them. In addition to the addition of the capacities of the stakeholders, the mutualistic symbiosis creates new opportunities that the separated partners do not have.

- **Expansion:** [5]act of expanding / taking up more land or space while developing / becoming greater in size, number, or amount...

This mechanism foster growing the considered community.

- **Centralization:** [5] action or process of bringing activities together in one place and under a single authority

Since the CECs are thought for decentralization systems to have the highest efficiency, this mechanism could not be the most adapted for CECs cross-services integration.

- **Uniformization:** standardize / make uniform / doing something conform to a standard

The Standard models and mechanisms are relevant for the CEC and to their deployment. Using this mechanism allows reducing deployment costs and makes perfect sense for CEC services cross-integration.

7.2. NEON CECs services Cross-integration

We presented in section 02 of this deliverable the process used to describe the existing services within NEON. To achieve T1.1 objectives we also need to consider exiting energy services within the existing or emerging energy communities to create new opportunities at the community level. To do so, we must first compare the existing services within each CEC through various dimensions to identify commonalities or differences and consider their cross-integration through an adapted mechanism.

We thus proposed to fulfil the “existing services comparison table” below.

Dimensions		Name of the existing service					
Strategic	Objectives						
Strategic	Interests						
Orga / social	Customers / users						
Orga / social	Customers' needs and pains / requirements						
Orga / social	Suppliers (internal)						
Orga / social	Partners (external)						
Orga / social	Suppliers and partners skills						
Orga / social	Suppliers and partners constraints						
Spatial	Location / places						
Temporal	Key timelines / moments						
Environmental	Info's and impacts						
Business	Type of business model						
Business	Costs and revenue items						
Legal	Type of contracts, info's						
Processes	Processes						
Functional	Activities / tasks						
Procedural	Procedures / standards / norms						
Technical	Tools / software						
Functional	Functionalities						
Technical	Equipment						
Informational	Key data						

Table 2 Existing services comparison table

This comparison table enables identifying common or complementary elements between services. These elements could be clues to envisage a cross-integration between two or more existing services for the benefit of the future CEC.

Once done, the conclusions should indicate the findings in terms of comparison, the cross-integration mechanisms to be used and the opportunities that could emerge from these cross-integration. To facilitate this task, each CEC must consider the following questions:

- What are the common / similar / complementary elements that appear between existing services?
- What are the cross-integration mechanisms that could be used?
- What are the opportunities that emerge from these cross-integration?

8. NEON’s CECS cross-services and related business opportunities

In line with the objectives of the deliverable D1.1, this section presents a comparison of the existing energy services identified earlier within each NEON’s project Citizen Energy community. This comparison has been performed to identify the possible synergies between the existing services, to create new opportunities and to generate added value to the community participants by cross integrating these services.

8.1. CEC 01 -BERCHIDDA

Dimensions		Local Energy Community	Collective Self consumption of PV production
Strategic	Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase social engagement on community and energy issues 2. Increase building’s energy systems efficiency 3. Improve building’s comfort 4. Add value to the city with more services (EV) 5. Energy and economic savings 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase share of renewable energy of total energy demand 2. Optimise the use of the energy produced by the PV plants on-site 3. Decrease total demand from the grid of Berchidda 4. Energy and economic savings 5. Take advantage of the national incentive of 160Euro/MWh on the energy self-produced and self-consumed 6. Reduce carbon footprint
	Interests	LEC non-technical service that aims to set up the social engagement and energy awareness	LEC energy sharing service
Organizational / social	Customers / users	all Berchidda Municipality citizens	all members of Berchidda CEC (prosumers and only consumers, residential/industrial/public)
	Customers’ needs and pains / requirements	increase energy consumption awareness, improve building’s energy efficiency	Maximize the exploitation of locally produced RES

	Suppliers (internal)	Energy4com, Gridability, PROSUME, R2M Energy, AXPO	Nesosnet, PROSUME, R2M Energy
	Partners (external)	Berchidda Municipality	Berchidda Municipality (DSO)
	Suppliers and partners skills	Pre-established contacts with the local community	Midac (residential storage batteries)
	Suppliers and partners constraints	Energy4com: Covid-19 pandemic hampered in-presence community meetings	Nesosnet: Delay in Smart Meter installations (commodity shortage, Covid-19 pandemic)
Spatial	Location / places	Berchidda Municipality Citizens' houses	Privately owned residential roofs of citizens Berchidda Municipality Storage Batteries installed in 20 homes
Temporal	Key timelines / moments	Recursive community meetings and events (min 2/year)	Energy storage (Midac): To support load shifting for DR 20 residential batteries of 5.1 kW of storage will be installed by March 2022
Environmental	Info and impacts	Improvement on residential heating and cooling systems energy efficiency and change from gas source system to electrical system, thus reduction of energy consumption and of CO2 emissions	Increase of the share of renewable energy on the total electricity demand, thus reduction of electricity demand from the grid produced by centralised plants from fossil fuels
Business	Type of business model	Cooperative model and Service contract	Service contract
Business	Costs and revenue items	Costs = Event organization, heat pumps and EV chargers installation and maintenance, smart meters installation Revenues = national incentives + energy shared	Costs = solar power plant installation and maintenance, battery energy storage installation and maintenance, smart meters installation Revenues = national incentives + energy shared
Legal	Type of contracts, info	Cooperative Association (LEC legal entity), EPC contracts, Audits	Smart contracts / PPA
Processes	Processes	1. Recruitment of members to the community 2. Legal formalisation of Berchidda CEC	1. PV production to cover building's consumption

		<p>3. Installation of smart meters and connection to the monitoring platform</p> <p>In parallel, for those who request an energy audit and energy efficiency works to their houses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inspection and survey of the building 2. Building's energy modelling 3. Development of different scenarios of retrofit 4. Offer to the end-user 5. Plan and design 6. Retrofit works and commissioning 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Surplus energy produced by PV is either stored in the battery or injected in the grid to be shared with another member of the community in need of it 3. Optimization of the energy fluxes through DR mechanisms 4. Valorisation of self-generated and self-consumed energy in the same hour in the perimeter of the CEC with national incentives through the PROSUME app
Functional	Activities / tasks	Community meetings and events, inspections and surveys for energy audits and retrofitting works	PV installation, Smart meter installation & connection, data flow establishment to the community platform, Prosumer DLT and APP enablement
Procedural	Procedures / standards / norms	<p>LEC non-technical service that aims to set up the social engagement and energy awareness</p> <p>D.Lgs 10/06/2020, n. 48: Implementation of Directive (EU) 2018/844 and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency</p> <p>DM 26/06/2015: Adaptation of the Decree of the Minister for Economic Development, 26 June 2009 - National Guidelines for the Energy Certification of Buildings</p>	<p>Article 42-bis of the Milleproroghe Decree 162/2019 (converted by Law no. 8/2020 of 28 February 2020)</p> <p>ARERA's Resolution 318/2020/R/eel and the DM of 16 September 2020 of the MiSE)</p> <p>Legislative Decree 199 of 8/11/2021, which implements the European RED II Directive on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.</p>

Technical	Tools / software	Social media, local newspaper, any communication tool to disseminate and raise awareness, Community's monitoring platform	Nesosnet Smart Meters and community platform, PROSUME DLT and APP
Functional	Functionalities	Engagement of citizens into virtuous behavioural change, Building's energy system retrofit	Demand response, Smart energy storage management, Collective peak shaving, Optimisation of electric flows within the REC
Technical	Equipment	Nesosnet Smart Meters (IoT energy Hub blockchain enabled): to cover at least 300 homes Energy Management Platform Electric heat pump systems: in around 10 residential houses EV charging stations: around 6 distributed in most strategic points of the city	Nesosnet Smart Meters (IoT energy Hub blockchain enabled): to cover at least 300 homes Energy storage (Midac): 20 residential batteries of 5.1 kW of storage
Informational	Key data	Berchidda Municipality information data (population, building's age, building's type, ...), buildings' consumption, PV production	PV production, domestic consumption, household composition, time of the day, weather forecast, day-ahead energy price, national incentives RSE, ARERA tariffs

Table 3 CEC 01 Existing energy services comparison table

Both of Berchidda CEC's existing services pursue the objective of providing environmental and socio-economic benefits, in addition to energy benefits, for the members and the local community in which they operate. Both also aim at a radical change of the market (demand side the former, the latter) by putting the production and distribution of electricity back in the hands of the citizens.

The community of Berchidda shows, starting from its strategic objectives and interests, a clear alignment with the will to involve citizens in an active participatory process of supply, management, and optimization of renewable energy resources. This is evident, in principle, from the Municipality's participation in electricity distribution services, through AEC, and its willingness to return an innovative electricity grid capable of distributing the burdens (and benefits) of autonomous renewable energy management within the CEC.

Since its foundation, the Berchidda CEC has seen a strong organizational synergy between the actors supporting the establishment of the CER, actors linked to the social, regulatory, and behavioral nature of the community, see for example Energy4com.

The integration mechanisms arise from the complementarity of the actors involved in the creation, management, and provision of optimization services of three front-end companies: GridAbility, its consortium companies Nesosnet and PROSUME, and Ener4com, an innovative cooperative in close operational connection with them.

The following mechanisms can be used to exploit the existing services:

- Leveraging Citizen Engagement: Leveraging the existing community of practice for the formation of the CEC services, tight personal connection, sense of cohesion will be leveraged with old-time Berchidda residents in a Municipality of 3000 people.
- Connecting distributed resources: Leveraging already installed distributed energy resources (photovoltaic + storage batteries) on top of the planned installations (20 heat pumps + 4 community EV charging stations) to increase the flexibility services that can be offered by the CEC grid while providing self-sufficiency in the Municipality.
- Diversification of PV installation by end-users: Berchidda targets 100 people for the setup of the CEC and the installation of PV production including (1) Residential users (prosumer), (2) Local wineries and cork industries (3) Public Municipality buildings and lighting, allowing better exploitation of energy efficiency (i.e. via demand response, MEVPP) .

Already in the establishment of the Energy Community, two clear opportunities for integration with the services offered for the optimization of PV self-consumption emerge:

1. Assessment of production and consumption profiles for the collection of CEC memberships
2. Creation of a social (people), digital and physical (energy) network, regulated, monitored and self-managed.

The integration of its services creates value for community members to:

- Reduce the energy expenditure of individual citizens and the community.
- Contribute to the transition towards distributed generation of energy from renewable sources.
- Increase the know-how of collective management of energy produced from PV and develop the local CEC economy.
- Improve the energy performance of individual members (consumer and prosumer) as well as the energy management costs of the municipality.
- Make technologically, economically, and financially aware energy decisions at the individual and community level.
- Invest part of the proceeds in projects of general interest to the local community, i.e. new installations at the individual and community level, supporting a sustainable entrepreneurial mindset in the area.

8.2. CEC02 -DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE

Dimensions		Power to grid	Energy efficiency	Sobriety
Strategic	Objectives	Maximize revenues with power plant energy	Optimize energy efficiency	Optimize energy usage
	Interests	Revenue's warranty Potential power-price independency	Decrease losses / increase PV revenue	Decrease energy waste
Orga / social	Customers / users	Apartment owner	Apartment owner	Apartment owner
	Customers' needs and pains / requirements	Solar power plant ROI	hot water production optimisation	Energy costs
	Suppliers (internal)	Conseil syndical & general owner assembly	Conseil syndical & general owner assembly	Conseil syndical & general owner assembly
	Partners (external)	Syndic-Enedis- Solar power plant installer?	ESCO	ESCO Sociologist oriented
	Suppliers and partners' skills	Solar power plant design, Enedis relation knowledge, economic ROI calculation	Building Energy efficiency Heat pump maintenance qualification QualiPAC QualiPV Esco analysis	Energy and human behaviour
	Suppliers and partners' constraints	Low price for studies, solar prediction uncertainty	consumption data measurement	Inhabitants' motivation during holidays
Spatial	Location / places	Residence city	DDLS residence	DDLS residence

Temporal	Key timelines / moments	from building design to commissioning	Periodic visit and on breakdown event	Daily
Environmental	Information and impacts	Solar power plant = 40 g /kWh	To be evaluated	Energy consumption
Business	Type of business model	Energy reselling	Services	services
Business	Costs and revenue items	Costs = solar power plant installation and maintenance Revenues = energy sold to grid	Costs: energy systems studies, equipment, and commissioning Revenues = comfort efficiency (€/°comfort)	Immediate costs measurable
Legal	Type of contracts, information	Standard Enedis contract PMO agreement	ESCO contract	CEC community
Processes	Processes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Register the installation on Enedis Website 2. Enedis connect (physically) the production on the grid 3. Production start injection to the grid 4. EDF to send the agreement validated 5. EDF to pay the energy each period 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Measurement 2. Data Analysis 3. Optimisation plan 4. Installation 5. Test 6. Follow up 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General assembly problem explanation 2. Software able to show consumption 3. Nudge 4. Follow up
Functional	Activities / tasks	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Register 2. Connect 3. Start solar production 4. Payment each period 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data measurement 2. Data analysis 3. Esco solutions defining 4. Setting up actions and control 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Software installation 2. Follow up behaviour 3. Results measurement
Procedural	Procedures / standards / norms	Energy Code (code de l'énergie)	Security procedure	No

Technical	Tools / software	Enedis web site Electric specific tools	energy Modelling-simulation tools (E+)	Software
Functional	Functionalities	The main part of solar power is self-consumed by common areas, melting of snow, the rest (#40%) is sold to EDF at a low price #90€/MWh)	Integration between DHW Electricity domestic usage consumption and solar production	Show energy consumption Show energy waste
Technical	Equipment	solar panels	Additional energy flow Sensors	no
Informational	Key data	Solar Installation economic study, Production prevision, Price of energy sold	Energy injected to the grid	Energy consumption Energy waste costs

Table 4 CEC 02 existing energy services comparison table

The main common element between the services listed in the previous table is the price of energy, so the question that arises is how to optimize consumption and solar power plant production to reduce the costs of energy for the stakeholders.

Thermal energy price is valued at 90€/MWh, electricity on the grid costs 180 /MWh and the solar energy cost must be evaluated in regard of the installation and maintenance costs. So, it becomes very clear that the optimization must be done starting with an economic calculation. The calculation will need data that probably we don't have yet and need to be measured on the site. This analysis also must be done in regard of emergent needs like electric mobility and storage.

Create new opportunities and generate value for Domaine de la source energy community stakeholders could be achieved by:

Analyse existing pains:

The cross-integration mechanism should be based on an economic analysis of energy balance of the systems. I think it should be straight connected with a carbon balance analysis because environment is also a question of the CEC stakeholders.

Maybe having a helicopter view with carbon and economic filters on the CEC systems optimization processes.

In fact, the cross-integration mechanism inherits of the stakeholders' requests and life analysis. So, probably a social analysis is a prerequisite of any cross-integration mechanism.

Open mind – similar problems

Another way of cross-integration is to analyse other activity market, in their energy transition. By example how automotive did this transition. What is a difference using a fuel motor car and an electric motor car? This analysis could open new ideas in this cross-integration process.

The first opportunity is the analysis describe above but probably, doing it will be possible to discover other opportunities new and valuable.

There are several opportunities we can explore:

- Energy travel: How is it possible to optimize the way of using energy considering that solar energy has a discontinuous production?

The new service “energy travel” is very similar to the travel organization with an electric car. There is a need of maintaining a level of comfort in the flats (global usage of the flat functions: heat, air quality, hot water, cooking, lighting...), with a limited quantity of energy during a slot of time depending on the meteorology. This is the same problem we had managing the energy of a high mountain refuge.

This new service needs a new approach with a new methodology, technology, behaviour analysis and acceptance of the change.

- Cross-optimization: What is the best solution for scheduling energy systems usage regarding simultaneously economics, carbon, and comfort costs optimization?

This new service needs cross skills including legal rules knowledge, energy market, technology of energy production and systems, behaviour, carbon balance. Combining in a team these skills, it could be possible to define a new methodology able to generate in a dynamic way the right, just, schedule for the usage of energy.

8.3. CEC 03- POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS

For analyzing possible business opportunities for different possibilities of CEC using the existing energy services (PV self-consumption, EV recharging points and storage), we must compare them and focusing about some aspects about strategic objectives and interests, typical customers and users, social achievements, legal aspects, technical issues and needs, way of management, etc.

For this reason, we have compared all these aspects in the following table for a better understanding:

Dimensions		PV Self consumption system	EV Recharging point	Storage
Strategic	Objectives	Energy Saving / Money Saving	Providing energy for e-mobility / Positioning in a booming sector / Studying economic payback rate for future investment	Energy Saving / Money Saving
Strategic	Interests	Cheap technology	Booming sector	Surplus generation from PV system stored
Organizational / Social	Customers / users	GFM (owner)	Owners of electrical vehicles	GFM (owner)
	Customers ' needs and pains / requirements	Reducing electrical bill / Being more efficient	Obtaining energy for recharging electrical Vehicles / minimizing recharging times / savings for mobility (compared to refuelling)	Reducing electrical bill / Being more efficient / Being more independent from the grid / Taking advantage of surplus generation
	Suppliers (internal)	GFM (owner)	GFMCA (owner) / GFM (installer and O&M)	GFM (owner)
	Partners (external)	Unión Fenosa / Gesternova	Unión Fenosa / Gesternova / Electromaps	Unión Fenosa / Gesternova (only for legal aspects and administrative register).
	Suppliers and	Unión Fenosa (measuring energy fed and purchased from the grid) Gesternova (electricity	Unión Fenosa (measuring energy purchased from the grid) Gesternova (electricity bill)	Unión Fenosa (not working during lifetime)

	partners' skills	bill and special discount for surplus energy)	Electromaps (payment platform for end users)	Gesternova (not working during lifetime)
	Suppliers and partners' constraints	Unión Fenosa (delay in administrative works, paying economic rates) Gesternova (reduced monetary quote for surplus production)	Unión Fenosa (delay in administrative works, paying economic rates) Gesternova (being careful about wrong prices for electricity) Electromaps (transactions errors for recharging, not alarms enough when something goes wrong)	Unión Fenosa (not working during lifetime) Gesternova (not working during lifetime)
Spatial	Location / places	Villacañas (Polígono Las Cabezas. Calle Las Cabezas 16. 45860 Villacañas - Toledo - SPAIN)	Villacañas (Polígono Las Cabezas. Calle Las Cabezas 16. 45860 Villacañas - Toledo - SPAIN)	Villacañas (Polígono Las Cabezas. Calle Las Cabezas 16. 45860 Villacañas - Toledo - SPAIN)
Temporal	Key timelines / moments	Legalization and installation: 4 months System Lifetime: 30 years	Legalization and installation: 4 months System Lifetime: 25 years	Legalization and installation: 4 months System Lifetime: 6 years
Environmental	Infos and impacts	There is not environmental impact (everything is integrated in the building)	There is not environmental impact (everything is integrated in the building)	Special treatment for a longer lifetime Special treatment for recycling.
Business	Type of business model	Electricity uses (using energy for ourselves)	Electricity uses (for EV recharging)	Electricity uses (using energy for us, taking advantage of the generation surplus).
	Costs and revenue items	Costs: corrective works, tools cost and worker's salary for O&M Revenue: 40% saving money from electrical bills	Costs: corrective works, tools cost and worker's salary Revenue: paying for end users payment platform managing.	Costs: corrective works, tools cost and worker's salary for O&M Revenue: 10% saving money from electrical bills
Legal	Type of contracts, information	Contract 1: GFM (owner) - Unión Fenosa (Grid Company) Contract 2: GFM (owner) - Gesternova (Market Agent)	Contract 1: GFMCA (owner) - Unión Fenosa (Grid Company) Contract 2: GFMCA (owner) - Gesternova (Market Agent)	Contract 1: GFM (owner) - Unión Fenosa (Grid Company) Contract 2: GFM (owner) - Gesternova (Market Agent)

			<p>Contract 3: GFMCA (owner) - GFM (installer – O&M)</p> <p>Contract 4: GFMCA (owner) - Electro maps (payment platform for end users)</p>	
<p>Processes</p>	<p>Processes</p>	<p>Energy generated from PV system involves a reduced energy imported from the grid. Surplus generation is stored in batteries at first and it could be fed into the grid if batteries are full. During night hours batteries are discharged. It involves a reduced consumption from the grid if we compare with the situation before the PV system installation.</p> <p>Every month, the grid company (Unión Fenosa) measures how much power has been imported and how much power has been exported by the owner of PV System (GFM). Unión Fenosa sends to the agent market (Gesternova) this information. The agent market (Gesternova) issues the electrical bill to GFM (owner) for paying for the electrical energy imported from the grid. This bill will show a special discount due to energy fed into the grid from surplus production.</p>	<p>Energy is imported from the grid for recharging electrical vehicles. It is measured by the Grid Company (Unión Fenosa) and they send to the market agent (Gesternova) this kind of information. Using this information, the market agent (Gesternova) issues the electrical bill to GFMCA (owner) for paying for the electrical energy imported from the grid.</p> <p>In parallel, when recharging process is being done, Electro maps collect money from end users due to this service. At the end of the month, Electro maps gives to GFMCA (owner) all the collected money, and GFMCA (owner) pays a quote for the management of payment platform to Electro maps.</p> <p>Once per year, GFMCA (owner) pays to GFM as installer for O&M. GFM does one or two reviews for ensuring everything is working properly.</p>	<p>Linked to self-consumption system</p>

Functional	Activities / tasks	Energy and money savings due to directly consumed energy from PV systems. Surplus production is fed into the grid. It involves a special discount in electrical bills.	Energy purchased from the grid for selling to end users for recharging electrical Vehicle's process.	Energy and money savings due to directly consumed energy from batteries, which has been stored during sunny hours from surplus generation
Procedural	Procedures / standards / norms	RD 244/2019	ITC-BT 52. REBT (RD 842/2002)	RD 244/2019
Technical	Tools / software	Monitoring software systems specific for Fronius inverters: Data manager 2.0. Fronius Solar Web online website for monitoring.	Webserver integrated in EV recharging stations. Electro maps manager website platform.	Monitoring software systems for Victron inverter / chargers: Venus GX. Victron VRM online website for monitoring.
Functional	Functionalities	Electrical current is fed into existing circuits by PV inverters. It needs to synchronize with existing voltage and frequency. PV inverters can make PV work in its efficient highest point thanks to a MPPT algorithm. All the electricity taken from the PV system is not taken from the grid. If more energy is needed, the grid will provide it.	Energy purchased for electrical vehicles recharging process.	Energy is stored in batteries from surplus production during sunny hours. Batteries are discharged for own use during night hours.
Technical	Equipment	104 PV modules, 6 PV inverters, meter for monitoring system	EV Recharging station. 50 kW DC (ChadeMo, CCS) and 40 kW AC (Mennekes)	Forty-eight lead-acid batteries (2V, 1000AH). 3 inverters / chargers, meter for monitoring system
Informational	Key data	Monitoring system, Electrical Bill, self-consumption rate, autarchy rate	Monitoring system, electrical bills, number of recharging processes, number of transaction errors, revenues from recharging services.	Monitoring system, Electrical Bill, self-consumption rate, autarchy rate

Table 5:CEC 03 existing services comparison table

As one can see, in the previous table, there are some common, similar, and complementary elements which could easily be exploited for cross-integration.

The main aspect is the complementary way of working between two of the currently existing services: PV self-consumption system and storage. Surplus production from PV self-consumption system (energy not consumed at the same time while it is being generated) is stored in batteries for an appropriated and efficient way of energy usage (for example during night hours). –This has been observed as both services are linked to the same installation and end user.

PV self-consumption and storage have the same objective: energy and money savings (the most appreciated aspect for stakeholders)

The same location for the three existing services is a clear advantage for cross-integration.

External partners like Unión Fenosa (Grid Company) and Gesternova (market agent) is another similarity between the three existing services. They will not participate in the future Energy Community because they do not have interest on it. But there is some important information related to the energy requirements on their websites and it could be used if it is necessary.

GFM is the owner of two existing services (PV self-consumption system and storage) and it is the responsible for O&M of the third existing service (EV recharging points, whose owner is GFMCA). It could be a possibility for a barter between GFM and GFMCA. GFM carries out O&M tasks and GFMCA allows free recharging process instead of paying.

Electricity uses the common way of working of three existing services, so it is another similarity.

A similar lifetime of three existing services components is another advantage because the model for a future energy community is valid for all three ones. There is not any service in a weaker position for future years.

For legalization we need the same period of time for three existing services. It is good because it does not involve delays for energy community development due to a certain energy service lags administrative works.

Three existing services have a very good monitoring system so the information for the energy community will be easily available for the cross-integration process.

Our recommendations for cross-integration mechanism for existing services are following ones:

Combination of services:

Self-consumption and storage can work together (as it happens in our case). Combination of these two services is not an obligation, but it is highly recommended. We could find also other devices that can be integrated and ensure independence of the system in the future.

It is also technically possible to combine the three existing energy services. The state of art for EV recharging points allows connecting PV modules and batteries for an integral way of operation.

It involves a direct connection between existing services, so the energy can flow from one to another, and it is a very efficient way of use.

Virtual Balance:

Sometimes it is not possible to install the devices close ones to each other's. In this case we could install the equipment wherever we could or where we have permission from the administration and/or the grid company. They will work by their own (there is no interconnection between them). Energy flow is measured, and it is agreed a shared used of it. At the end, the result is the same as if all existing energy services are connected, even though there is not any electrical connection. This is possible thanks to an internal agreement between all stakeholders (energy providers and end users). All of them compensate ones to each other's using energy (kWh) and money (euros). It is an interesting way for cross-integration process, and it is exactly which it is expected to implement in this energy community for this pilot: POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS.

Energy barter:

This scenario is very similar to the previous one. It is another way for cross integration of these three existing services (storage, pv self-consumption, EV recharging points) and others. In this case there could be a barter between different stakeholders. For example, according to our case. GFMCA is the owner of one EV recharging point. For O&M works, GFM is signed. Once O&M works have been done by GFM, GFMCA does not pay money to GFM. Instead of this, GFM could charge their electric cars in this EV recharging station for free.

Let's imagine another possible example. Some storage systems are portable. Some people use these kinds of solutions for working activities in remote areas. There could be two stakeholders: owner of one solar panel-based self-consumption system and owner of portable batteries. Five batteries could be charged using surplus production from PV self-consumption system. The owner of the batteries uses four of his own batteries for some works wherever they could be. But one battery is lent to the owner of self-consumption system for reducing their consumption from the grid during night hours.

It is seen that money is not used. There are some energy barterers for compensating due to energy services.

Some great opportunities emerge from these cross-integration mechanisms.

There is one big opportunity thanks to these cross-integrations processes. It is the possibility of increasing the number of energy services development. Many times, there are a lot of projects that are not possible due to administrative restrictions, a lack of permission from the electrical grid company, economic aspects, constructive reasons, etc.

The possibility of combining energy services, enabling them for working together, multiplies the probability of success for many renewable projects (PV systems, storage, Wind systems, EV recharging stations, etc.).

D1. Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes

For example, let's imagine we would like to install some EV recharging stations. But the grid company does not allow us because there is not a strong connection to the grid due to a small size of distribution wires in our area. So, we decide to install PV modules and batteries to reduce the electricity needs from the grid. This entails the disappearance of the argument put forward by the electricity company.

8.4. CEC 04 -STAINS CITY

To analyse possible business opportunities for CEC STAINS based on the existing energy services provided by STAIN energy community stakeholders, a comparison of these services thought various dimensions has been performed in the table below, focusing on the objectives and the value of the services, the users of the services and their needs, the technical and functional activities, the business, social and environmental impacts.

The results from this analysis should allow to identify the most promising mechanisms for CEC STAIN services cross integration and to envisage the cross-integration between two or more existing energy services.

Dimensions		Facility Management	PV Self consumption Scheme	Green H2 production
Strategic	Objectives	Efficient exploitation of the building and its technical equipment. Reduction of OPEX cost while maximizing comfort in the building.	Produce local renewable energy, with individual self-consumption as much as possible and share locally the surplus of energy available.	Production of green H2 energy for research and learning purposes.
	Interests	Reduce the global energy consumption (with possible energy savings) and improve the environmental impact of the buildings and the businesses.	Reduce the energy supply cost for the building and improve the environmental impact with the generation of a local renewable energy source.	Test and validate new technologies. New area of expertise to develop for a renewable and green energy.

Organizational/ Social	Customers / users	Offices and buildings users/occupants (ENGIE CRIGEN and Industreet)	Industreet (producer and direct self-consumption) and CRIGEN (with a collective self-consumption scheme)	ENGIE Collaborators (and mainly ENGIE Lab H2)
	Customers' needs and pains / requirements	Comfort and security in the building, problem with technical equipment and maintenance, energy bill consumption in the building	Use of local energy production to reduce the dependency on the grid and control the energy bill. Sell electricity surplus to generate extra revenue.	Hydrogen provision for testing new technologies.
	Suppliers (internal)	Facility managers	Industreet (owner)	ENGIE Lab H2
	Partners (external)	Energy providers, Equipment manufacturers (for support), BMS integrator (for support)	DSO, PV surplus electricity buyer for grid reinjection, facility management, Enogrid	H2 equipment manufacturer
	Suppliers and partners' skills	Facility managers: supervise the building operation Energy providers: sell energy to the building occupants BMS integrator: can provide support and help regarding the use of the BMS.	Industreet + facility management: Supervision of the PV production and the overall operation of the self-consumption scheme. DSO: supervise the collective self-consumption scheme. Enogrid: follow the energy transfer between the member of the collective self-consumption.	ENGIE Lab H2: Supervision of the H2 production. H2 equipment manufacturer: provide support on the request for a proper operational usage of their equipment.

	Suppliers and partners constraints	Facility managers: technical equipment usability.	DSO: providing an accurate breakdown of the energy consumption/distribution between the different partners.	ENGIE Lab H2: availability of the electrolyze and management of the different experimentations using the same equipment.
Spatial	Location / places	Pierrefitte-Stains, Île-de-France	Pierrefitte-Stains, Île-de-France	Pierrefitte-Stains, Île-de-France
Temporal	Key timelines / moments	Periodic visit and supervision, intervention on breakdown event	Digital supervision in real time	Regular supervision of the production
Environmental	Information and impacts	Reducing energy consumption has a positive impact on the environmental footprint of the building	Producing and consuming local renewable energy help to reduce the environmental footprint of the buildings and the businesses	Production of an innovative energy vector, whose carbon content can be very low (if produce with green electricity) and doesn't produce any pollution when used.
Business	Type of business model	O&M contract between the facility manager or Energy Performance Contract (with engagement on energy reduction)	Investment (PV installation) to realize energy bill savings and sell PV to the local partner (collective self-consumption scheme) or the grid	H2 Energy production that can be sold.

	Costs and revenue items	Manpower to operate the maintenance in the building, energy savings if EPC contract	Energy bill reduction, injection to the grid and market sale	Costs: electricity sourcing, equipment and supervision
Legal	Type of contracts, info's	O&M Contracts between the building occupants and the facility manager (ENGIE CRIGEN Buildings and Industreet)	Agreement and participation to the collective self-consumption scheme	Energy furniture agreement/contract
Processes	Processes	Supervision of equipment, maintenance and security, supervision of thermal comfort in the building, follow the water and energy consumption in the building	Production of renewable electricity thanks to the PV panels. The energy available is first used as much as possible on the building of Industreet and the surplus available can be sold to ENGIE CRIGEN for their own use.	Electricity is used in a electrolyze to produce hydrogen. The hydrogen is then stored under pressure (bottles) for transportation.
Functional	Activities / tasks	Supervision of equipment, maintenance, supervision of comfort in the building	Follow-up of the energy transfer and billing of the energy transfer from Industreet to ENGIE CRIGEN.	Production of H2 gas from electricity. Storage in H2.
Procedural	Procedures / standards / norms	OEM standards	DSO procedure for self-consumption scheme	French "IPCE" regulation
Technical	Tools / software	Monitoring and BMS	PV inverters and Enogrid platform	Monitoring (to be confirmed)
Functional	Functionalities	Optimize energy consumption	Production and self-consumption (local or collective) of local renewable PV production	Production of H2

Technical	Equipment	Building management systems are available to monitor the different equipment.	PV panels, inverters and Enogrid platform for supervision.	H2 Electrolyser, compressors, and high-pressure H2 storage.
Informational	Key data	Water and energy consumption, temperatures in the building, HVAC operational data	Electricity consumption/injection, Total PV production, Self-consumption rate	H2 production and equipment availability.

Table 6: CEC 04 Existing energy services comparison table

Both services listed in the previous table (the facility management and the PV self-consumption) aim to reduce the energy bills and the environmental impact of the buildings and the businesses, for both ENGIE CRIGEN and Industreet, regarding the pilot scenarios. In terms of environmental impact, H2 production is particularly relevant in combination with the local renewable production of electricity.

The need for electricity to power building energy systems and to produce Hydrogen make them mutually complementary and reinforcing with the local PV production that is now capped by the system owner to avoid any grid injections. The surplus of renewable electricity could be sold or transfer to ENGIE CRIGEN. There is as well a certain flexibility in the H2 production by using storage and BMS control that is complementary with the intermittency and variation of the PV production.

The same localization and the involvement of the same actors are a key element to make first requirement is the introduction of a collective self-consumption scheme. The proximity of local hydrogen production in ENGIE CRIGEN is also an opportunity for Industreet who would be interested in developing new training and expertise around hydrogen for their students.

The NEON cross-integration mechanisms that could be used in the project are mainly combination mechanism of the different services. Now, Industreet is artificially limiting the PV production because he doesn't have any possibility to reinject it on the national grid. If the surplus of energy was made available to ENGIE CRIGEN, it could be used for the electrical need of the building, and it would be as well possible to use it for the H2 production.

The H2 production being associated to some storage capacities, it would be possible to pilot the H2 production to prioritize the production when PV electricity is available and not consumed. On a similar way, the building energy systems could be controlled to some extent to adapt its energy consumption to maximize the energy consumption when there is a PV production.

Being both interested in innovation and new technologies around energy, ENGIE CRIGEN and Industreet could potentially share skills and expertise around hydrogen. Some common work or partnership on the subject could be a way to proceed.

The main opportunities of these cross integration would be the following:

- Maximizing the use of the energy that is produced locally and reducing the environmental impact of the buildings and the local activities and businesses. It requires new way of piloting and optimizing energy consumption at the community level when there is a local energy production.

- Reducing the energy bills through the self-consumption scheme or lowering the dependency on the energy market, in a general context of increasing prices.
- Share the possibility of working with an innovating resource (H2) in terms of training and expertise as it is a promising energy vector for a decarbonized future.
- Testing the possibilities regarding the deployment of new services dedicated to local energy communities.

9. Summary and key takeaways for NEON

In NEON project, four Citizen Energy Communities have been selected BERCHIDDA, DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE, POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS, and STAINS CITY distributed among three European countries, namely, Italy, France, and Spain. In this deliverable a characterization of the pilot sites is given, while the main differences between the four pilot sites (taking into consideration the type of energy uses to be addressed by local renewable energy production, the level of progress regarding the installation of smart devices inside homes, and the type of flexibilities) will be studied during the pilot experiments.

- In Berchidda, the energy uses such as heating and cooling or domestic hot water and specific uses of electricity will be studied to shift them to moments of local PV generation.
- In Domain de la source, particular attention will be given to the optimization of storing thermal energy and HP operation for space heating, jointly with the flexibly on other electricity uses inside homes.
- In Poligono industrial las Cabezas that consists of multiple PV installations, a wind turbine, 3 EV chargers and a lead-acid battery, the goal is to operate the assets as a single network and to utilize all the existing renewable plants at a single point.
- Finally, Stain city building meets the requirements of E+C- French label with H2 panels, installation of batteries and PVs. where any excess electricity will be distributed to the neighborhood or exchanged with the grid.

Deliverable 1.1 presents the assessment methodology (see Section 5) and proceeds with the assessment of existing energy services, offered by NEON CEC's stakeholders. Based on a series of workshops organized with the pilot owners, the consortium gained a clear understanding of the existing situation at the pilot sites. As a result, the existing energy services offered by NEON's emerging CEC's, the different actors, and their links with the services within each CEC environment were identified and documented, as follows:

- for the Berchidda pilot – 2 main services (see Section 6.1);
- for Domaine de la Source pilot - three services (see Section 6.2);
- for Poligono industrial las Cabezas - 3 services (see Section 6.3); and
- for Stain city - 3 services (see Section 6.4).

This deliverable also gives an overview of the cross-integration mechanisms (in Section 7). It closes with NEON's CECs cross-services and related opportunities. Based on this analysis, it is observed that there are some common, similar, and complementary elements which could easily be explored for cross-integration of services. The main aspects of the complementary way of working between two of currently existing services are provided for each Citizen Energy Community.

Finally, this deliverable sets the ground for **T1.2: Service offer specification and business planning** (co-creation process) and **T1.3: Cross-sectoral arrangements and stakeholder interaction**, by clearly extracting the existing services, identifying possible cross-services, and positioning the stakeholders of the emerging CECs. These services that pre-exist within each Citizen community and described in this deliverable will be reconsidered, fine-tuned and new opportunities might be identified in the co-creation process to be implemented within NEON project in task T1.2.

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ANNEXES

Annex I services selection criteria

The criteria list below has been defined by T1.1 participants during T1.1 first workshop and used for the existing energy efficiency services identification and selection.

Criteria Name	Criteria Short Description
Energy savings	Energy Savings from EPC and P4P implementation.
Monetary savings	Money savings from consumers and producers.
Comfort improvement	Comfort improvement from participation in Energy Communities
User awareness	Raising awareness, building capacities, thereby empowering Indicator that will measure the awareness raising and knowledge sharing (qualitative).
User control	Degree to which users feel in charge of their experience with the technology.
User acceptance	Indicator aggregating perceived usefulness, ease of use and behavior, possibly mediated by sensory appeal.
Size of the CEC	Number and type of stakeholders.
Environmental impact	GHG, Visual, sound, etc.
Secure and privacy	
Replicability	How much work is needed to adapt the service to different contexts (country, climate, etc.). In how many different contexts has the service been tested.
Satisfaction	Asses the overall degree of content of the user belonging to the CEC in terms of participation, contributing to green transition and energy justice.
Scalability	
Interoperability	Ability of a system (or system of system) to work with or use the parts of another system/services.
Type of the CEC	Citizen Energy Community types.
Open and voluntary satisfaction	The end user should have access to the service without significant barriers to entry and should also be able to exit the service under reasonable terms
Service cost equalization	Shared cost and benefits to support weaker sections of the CEC

Annex II services description Template

CEC 01 -BERCHIDDA services

D1. Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes

CEC02 -DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE services

D1. Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes

D1. Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes

CEC 03: POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS , Villacañas (Toledo), Spain

D1. Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes

D1. Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes

CEC 04 -STAINS CITY services

